

Notes

Chemical Investigation of the Bark and Heartwood of *Grewia asiatica* Linn.

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GREWIA *asiatica* Linn. (Tiliaceae) is an important medicinal plant and its roots, bark, leaves and fruits have been used in various ailments¹ like, rheumatism, stomachic etc. In view of these important properties and the fact that almost no work has been done so far on this plant, a chemical investigation of the plant has been undertaken in this laboratory. Preliminary studies on some sister species, *G. populifolia* Vahl²⁻³ and *G. tiliifolia* Vahl⁴ have, however, been reported.

The dried and powdered bark of the plant (2 kg) was extracted with benzene for 36 hrs. The benzene extract (15 g) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (60°–80°) yielded a product, which on crystallization (methanol), gave a colourless product A (250mg) m.p. 198°–200°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test and Noller's test and appeared to be a triterpene. It was identified as β -amyrin by m.m.p. determination, co-TLC and co-IR with an authentic specimen of the compound.

Further elution with petroleum-ether : benzene (4 : 1) and crystallization from methanol gave shining white flakes of product B (150 mg) m.p. 136°–7°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test, a yellow colour with tetranitromethane and was identified as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. determination ; co-TLC with an authentic specimen of the compound, and preparation of its acetate m.p. 128° and benzoate m.p. 144°–6°.

Elution with benzene yielded a product which on crystallization (methanol) gave a solid C (250 mg) m.p. 251°–2°. It gave positive Libermann-Burchard test and Noller's test and appeared to be a triterpene. It was identified as betulin by m.m.p. determination, co-TLC and co-IR with an authentic specimen of the compound and preparation of its diacetate m.p. 215°–1° and dibenzoate m.p. 180°.

Powdered heartwood (4 kg) of the plant was extracted with petroleum ether (60°–80°) for 40 hrs. The petroleum ether extract (10 gm) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) yielded a product which was identified as β -sitosterol.

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Stability of Solid Chloramin-T Towards X- and Gamma Radiation

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CHLORAMINE-T (CAT), the sodium salt of *N*-chloro *p*-toluene sulphonamide has found extensive use as an analytical reagent. Speculations about its use as a primary standard have led to controversial reports regarding its stability to heat and light¹. In the present communication, the authors have examined the stability of the solid CAT and anhydrous CAT towards ionizing radiations (X – and Co⁶⁰ gamma rays) and some preliminary results have been reported.

The experimental procedure has been described elsewhere². X-irradiations were done with 30 KVP Cu-K α radiation in an X-ray machine supplied by Radon House, Calcutta, India.

The extent of decomposition in the compounds was determined by comparison of the iodometric titer of the sample exposed to radiation with that of an unexposed sample. The percentage decomposition of the compounds was found to increase more or less linearly with the increase in absorbed dose. $G_{(-CAT)}$ values (number of molecules decomposing per 100 eV of radiant energy absorbed) are given in Table 1. A slight dose rate dependence is observed in the case of gamma irradiated CAT.